

MAXWELL EQUATIONS AND THE PROPAGATION OF ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVES

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Abstract – This work presents a study on Maxwell's four equations in integral and differential forms that are based on the concepts of Gauss, Faraday, and Lens Laws, Ampère's circuit, and how these equations validate the existence of electromagnetic waves and their propagation in addition to the importance of these concepts for the development of applications in different areas.

Palavras-chave: Electromagnetism, Electromagnetic Field, Electric Field, Magnetic Field, Antennas.

INTRODUCTION

Electromagnetic waves (EMW) are a means of transporting energy or information, requiring a source to radiate them [1] with time-varying current [2,3]. When propagating, EMW are wavelike [1], but as they are at long distances from their origin, that is, when their distance is much greater than their wavelength (λ), they are flat and uniform, with sinusoidal variation in time, defined length and in this region are defined as far field. The near field is the region where the electromagnetic field is close to the radiating element, which can be, for example, the antenna, storing energy in a reactive (capacitive) field without any contribution to the radiated power [2].

A physical medium is not required, but when propagating in a dielectric medium, EMW lose energy due to the conductivity (σ) of the medium, and the material loss tangent can quantify such losses. It is worth noting that the behavior of the medium does not depend only on the physical characteristics of σ , permeability (μ), and dielectric constant (ϵ) but also on the operating frequency to which the medium is subjected, being able to be a good conductor in low and a suitable dielectric at high [1].

OEMs that, through electronic elements or devices that vary the current with time, can be applied in 5G communication [4], medical imaging [5-7], radars [5,6,8], satellites [8] and sterilization of viruses and bacteria [9].

Maxwell, through his equations, predicted the existence of EMW based on two concepts: the electric field (E) produced by a time-varying magnetic field (H) and the H that is produced from the time-varying E [2]. That is, the E and H fields are time-varying and interdependent. Therefore, to be an electromagnetic field, it must satisfy Maxwell's equations [1].

This work aims to present a study of Maxwell's four equations precisely because of their importance in describing the existence of EMW through equations.

DEVELOPMENT

Maxwell's four equations, whether in differential or integral form, predicted the existence of EMW and were based on Faraday and Lens, Gauss, and Ampère's law.

In this section, the four equations will be shown, in which the symbols in bold are large vectors.

(a) Maxwell's First Equation

The first equation presented in this work is Gauss' Law, which defines that the electric flux that passes

through a closed surface equals the total charge on that surface [1,2] defined by Equation (1).

$$\oint_S \mathbf{D} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = \int_V \rho_v dv \quad (1)$$

Where the closed surface integral of the electric flux density $\mathbf{D}$ with surface bounded by the differential of two surface coordinates $d\mathbf{S}$ is equal to the volume integral of the volumetric charge density is ρ_v with volume bounded by the differential of the coordinates of a volume dv [1].

By applying the divergence theorem in the integral form of Maxwell's Equation (1), the point or differential form is obtained, according to Equation (2).

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_v \quad (2)$$

In it, we have that $\nabla \cdot$ it is the divergent vector operator that defines the flow that passes over a surface of small dimensions of a given volume that tends to zero [2].

(b) Maxwell's Second Equation

It is referred to as the Law of Conservation of Magnetic flux, where H is not conservative but flux. This leads us to infer that the magnetic flux line is closed, and it is not known where it starts and ends, indicating that there is no isolated magnetic charge, so Gauss' law of conservation of magnetic flux is given by the integral of Equation (3) [1,2].

$$\oint_S \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$\mathbf{B}$ is the magnetic density flux vector at a closed surface in this case. The equation is obtained in differential form by applying the divergence theorem, as explained by Equation (4).

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Equations (3) in integral form and (4) in differential form indicate that a magnetic field has neither source nor sink [1]. It is worth noting that Maxwell's first and second equations, based on Gauss' laws exposed in this work, are valid for static and time-varying fields, unlike the next two, which are valid only for varying fields [2].

(c) *Maxwell's Third Equation*

Based on the concepts of Faraday and Lens Law, defined by Equation (5), where H is a time variable that produces an electromotive force (emf), that is, an induced voltage, promoting the generation of current in a closed circuit in which the emf is in the opposite flow to the field that produced it [1,2].

$$\oint_L \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{L} = - \int_S \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \cdot d\mathbf{S} \quad (5)$$

The integral of a closed path of length L has a vector electric intensity field E with a path delimited by the differential of the coordinates of path dL . Equation (5) represents the emf, opposite to the flux and variable in time $\frac{\partial B}{\partial t}$, on a given surface delimited by dS [1]. Applying Stokes' theorem, Maxwell's Equation is obtained in the differential form [2], as presented in Equation (6).

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = - \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (6)$$

Thus, $\nabla \times \mathbf{E}$ represents the curl that indicates that, on an infinitesimal surface, the vectors of a vector field (in this case, electric) are moving away from or towards an average vector of the surface. This vector field is associated with the electric field strength. According to Equation (6), the curl is related to the rate of change of the magnetic flux in line with time [1,2].

(d) *Maxwell's Fourth Equation*

Based on Ampère's circuit law, the vector field of magnetic intensity H in a closed path and delimited by the coordinate differential dL , is precisely equal to the direct current involved in the path. However, with the E varying in time, there is a displacement current with density (J) and, consequently, a rate of change in time of the electric flux density $\frac{\partial D}{\partial t}$ in a closed surface, which results in the integral form of Equation (7) [2].

$$\oint_L \mathbf{H} \cdot d\mathbf{L} = \int_S \left(\mathbf{J} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} \right) \cdot d\mathbf{S} \quad (7)$$

Equation (8) represents the point form of Maxwell's fourth equation: the curl $\nabla \times \mathbf{H}$ of the magnetic field is equal to the sum of J with flux rate D .

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} \quad (8)$$

CONCLUSION

Electromagnetic waves contributed to the evolution of different industrial, military, or medical areas, providing a better quality of life for society. We can highlight the wide use of wireless communication today and the advent of industry 4.0, in which communication and data transfer are significant, so Maxwell's equations are essential factors in these developments.

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